

The GCD Triple Method: An Elementary and Combinatorial Alternative to p -adic Valuation

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Abstract

In the vast field of mathematics, particularly in number theory, the topic of greatest common divisor and least common multiple holds a distinctive place. Driven by our curiosity about mathematics and number theory, we encountered the first problem of the 2020 USEMO while working on number theory problems for mathematics olympiads. This problem asked participants to determine the positive integer values that a ratio formed by the least common multiples of three positive integers could take. Although there were various solutions to this problem, the solution suggested by the problem authors employed a challenging technique, such as the p -adic valuation, which is beyond the typical high school level. However, as we worked on this problem, we discovered that it could be solved using a more elementary technique. We found that this triple GCD method that we noticed while tackling the problem was more straightforward than the primary solution, which relied on complex concepts like the p -adic valuation and the Lifting The Exponent Lemma (*i.e.* *LTE*). Motivated by this observation, we decided to apply this technique to other problems to see if it could be similarly effective. Indeed, as with the USEMO problem, our technique simplified the solutions to certain problems. Ultimately, we realized that the method we developed could solve some problems of IMO level typically addressed by p -adic valuation in a much easier and more concise manner. We also show that the technique naturally generalizes to n integers via the $\binom{n}{2}$ pairwise gcds, which exposes an explicitly combinatorial structure underlying the problems we treat.

Keywords: Greatest Common Divisor, Least Common Multiple, Lifting the Exponent Lemma, p -adic valuation, Combinatorial Number Theory.

1. Introduction

In number theory, a broad branch of mathematics, concepts such as LTE and p -adic valuation can be challenging to grasp for high school students. While working on some Olympiad problems solved using this lemma, we developed a method that allows for much easier and more concise solutions to problems that utilize LTE or p -adic valuation. Our approach incorporates the lemmas related to p -adic valuation on the greatest common divisor (*that is*, gcd) and the least common multiple (*i.e.* lcm). These lemmas are described below. Throughout, gcd and lcm denote the greatest common divisor and least common multiple, respectively. Pairwise coprimality means $\gcd(u, v) = 1$ for any two distinct variables among the set in question.

Definition: The function $\nu_p(n)$ is defined for a prime p and a positive integer n as the highest power t such that p^t divides n . Due to this definition, the function $\nu_p(n)$ possesses certain properties.

Lemma 1: For positive integers x and y , x divides y if and only if $\nu_p(x) \leq \nu_p(y)$ for every prime p .

Lemma 2: For any integers x, y , and any prime p , the equality $\nu_p(xy) = \nu_p(x) + \nu_p(y)$ holds.

Lemma 3: For any prime p and positive integers x, n , the equality $\nu_p(x^n) = n \cdot \nu_p(x)$ holds.

Lemma 4: For any prime p and positive integers x and y , the inequality $\nu_p(x + y) \geq \min(\nu_p(x), \nu_p(y))$ is true.

Lemma 5: For any prime p and positive integers x and y , $\nu_p(\gcd(x, y)) = \min\{\nu_p(x), \nu_p(y)\}$ and $\nu_p(\text{lcm}(x, y)) = \max\{\nu_p(x), \nu_p(y)\}$

2. Methodology or Approach

The greatest common divisor and the least common multiple of positive integers a and b are fundamental concepts in arithmetic and number theory. The greatest common divisor of a and b is defined as the largest positive integer that divides both a and b . Similarly, the greatest common divisor of three or more positive integers, denoted $\gcd(a, b, c, \dots)$ is defined as the largest positive integer that divides all given integers. (Wolfram Mathworld, 2003).

In arithmetic and number theory, the least common multiple of two integers a and b is defined as the smallest positive integer that is divisible by both a and b (Wikipedia, 2012). Fermat's Method of Descent is the idea to prove an equation has no integral solutions, show one solution forces the existence of a smaller solution, leading to

$$a_1 > a_2 > a_3 > \dots > 0$$

which is impossible in $\mathbb{Z}_{>0}$. (Conrad, 2008)

Some problems were observed to have multiple solution approaches, including the use of the lifting the exponent lemma and the p -adic function. Upon further investigation, it became apparent that these two methods are quite challenging for high school students preparing for exams. As a result, we developed a new method to make the solution of these problems significantly easier and more concise. Our method proved to considerably simplify the problem-solving process. The problems examined were taken from the IMO, EMC, BAMO, ELMO, and Taiwan exams. Figure 1 shows the IMO logo.

Figure 1: IMO logo

3. Applications

First, let's examine the following lemmas to define our method.

- Lemma 1: Let a , b , and c be positive integers such that $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$. Then, there exist pairwise coprime integers x, y, z such that

$$\gcd(a, b) = d \cdot x$$

$$\gcd(a, c) = d \cdot y$$

$$\gcd(c, b) = d \cdot z$$

Proof of Lemma 1: If $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$, then d must divide each of $\gcd(a, b)$, $\gcd(a, c)$, and $\gcd(b, c)$. Hence, there exist positive integers x, y, z such that

$$\gcd(a, b) = d \cdot x, \quad \gcd(a, c) = d \cdot y, \quad \gcd(b, c) = d \cdot z.$$

We will now show that x, y , and z are pairwise coprime.

Assume, for the sake of contradiction, that they are not. Without loss of generality, suppose that $\gcd(x, y) = t > 1$. Then dt divides each of a, b , and c , implying that

$$\gcd(a, b, c) = d \cdot t$$

contradicts the assumption of $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$. Therefore, x, y , and z must be pairwise coprime.

- Lemma 2(GCD Triple Method): Let a, b , and c be positive integers such that $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$. Then, there exist positive integers x, y , and z such that the equalities $\gcd(a, b) = d \cdot x$, $\gcd(a, c) = d \cdot y$ and $\gcd(b, c) = d \cdot z$ hold. Furthermore, there exist pairwise coprime positive integers α, β , and γ such that the following equalities hold:

$$a = d \cdot x \cdot y \cdot \alpha$$

$$b = d \cdot x \cdot z \cdot \beta$$

$$c = d \cdot y \cdot z \cdot \gamma$$

Proof: Using Lemma 1, since x, y , and z are pairwise coprime, it follows that dxy divides a , dxz divides b , and dyz divides c . Hence, there exist positive integers α, β , and γ such that

$$a = d \cdot x \cdot y \cdot \alpha, \quad b = d \cdot x \cdot z \cdot \beta, \quad c = d \cdot y \cdot z \cdot \gamma.$$

Substituting these into the expressions for the greatest common divisors, we can verify that $\gcd(a, b) = dx$, $\gcd(a, c) = dy$, and $\gcd(b, c) = dz$.

Assume the contrary, and without loss of generality, suppose that $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = t > 1$.

Then we would have

$$\gcd(a, b) = dxt,$$

which contradicts the fact that $\gcd(a, b) = dx$. Therefore, α , β , and γ must also be pairwise coprime.

With the help of our technique (GCD Triple Method), certain problems from prestigious mathematical olympiads were solved in a much simpler and faster manner compared to the solutions provided by the problem proposers. For example, let us examine Problem 1 from USEMO (United States Ersatz Math Olympiad) 2020.

3.1 USEMO 2020 Problem 1

What positive integers can be expressed in the form

$$\frac{\text{lcm}(x, y) + \text{lcm}(y, z)}{\text{lcm}(x, z)}$$

for at least one triple of positive integers x, y, z

Solution: Let a, b, c , and d be positive integers such that

$$\gcd(x, y, z) = d, \quad \gcd(x, y) = a \cdot d, \quad \gcd(x, z) = b \cdot d, \quad \gcd(y, z) = c \cdot d.$$

Then, there exist positive integers x_1, y_1 , and z_1 such that

$$x = d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot x_1, \quad y = d \cdot a \cdot c \cdot y_1, \quad z = d \cdot b \cdot c \cdot z_1.$$

Furthermore, by the definition of LCM (Least Common Multiple), we have:

$$\text{lcm}(x, y) = d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot x_1 \cdot y_1,$$

$$\text{lcm}(x, z) = d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot x_1 \cdot z_1,$$

$$\text{lcm}(y, z) = d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1.$$

Now substitute these values into the equation:

$$\frac{\text{lcm}(x, y) + \text{lcm}(y, z)}{\text{lcm}(x, z)} = \frac{d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot x_1 \cdot y_1 + d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1}{d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot x_1 \cdot z_1}.$$

By simplifying the term $d \cdot a \cdot b \cdot c$, we get:

$$\frac{x_1 \cdot y_1 + y_1 \cdot z_1}{x_1 \cdot z_1}.$$

Since this expression is an integer, every integer that divides the denominator must

also divide the numerator. Given that x_1 divides $x_1 \cdot y_1 + y_1 \cdot z_1$, it follows that x_1 must divide $y_1 \cdot z_1$. However, since x_1, y_1, z_1 are pairwise coprime, we have $x_1 = 1$. Similarly, since z_1 divides $x_1 \cdot y_1 + z_1 \cdot y_1$, using the same reasoning, $z_1 = 1$.

Substituting these values back into the equation, we find:

$$\frac{\text{lcm}(x, y) + \text{lcm}(y, z)}{\text{lcm}(x, z)} = \frac{x_1 \cdot y_1 + y_1 \cdot z_1}{x_1 \cdot z_1} = 2 \cdot y_1.$$

Thus all positive integers which can be expressed in the given form are even. Since y_1 is a positive integer, any even positive integer can be expressed in this form. Therefore, the answer is all positive even integers.

Now, let us examine Problem 4 from the Bay Area Mathematical Olympiad (BAMO) 2018.

3.2 BAMO 2018 Problem 4

Show that if a, b, c are nonzero integers such that

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{c} + \frac{c}{a}$$

is an integer, then abc is a perfect cube.

Solution: By equating denominators, it is found that the expression

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{c} + \frac{c}{a} = \frac{a^2c + b^2a + c^2b}{abc}$$

is an integer. Let $\gcd(a, b, c) = k$. If we divide both the numerator and the denominator by k^3 , we obtain a situation where $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$ and the statement we want to prove remains unchanged. Thus, without loss of generality, we can assume $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$.

For positive integers x, y, z , let

$$\gcd(a, b) = x, \quad \gcd(a, c) = y, \quad \gcd(b, c) = z.$$

Then, there exist pairwise coprime positive integers a_1, b_1, c_1 such that

$$a = x \cdot y \cdot a_1, \quad b = x \cdot z \cdot b_1, \quad c = z \cdot y \cdot c_1.$$

Substituting these into the expression, we get:

$$\frac{a^2c + b^2a + c^2b}{abc} = \frac{(y^3 \cdot x^2 \cdot z \cdot a_1^2 \cdot c_1 + x^3 \cdot z^2 \cdot y \cdot b_1^2 \cdot a_1 + z^3 \cdot y^2 \cdot x \cdot c_1^2 \cdot b_1)}{x^2 \cdot y^2 \cdot z^2 \cdot a_1 \cdot b_1 \cdot c_1}.$$

Dividing the numerator and the denominator by $x \cdot y \cdot z$, the expression simplifies to:

$$\frac{y^2 \cdot x \cdot a_1^2 \cdot c_1 + x^2 \cdot z \cdot b_1^2 \cdot a_1 + z^2 \cdot y \cdot c_1^2 \cdot b_1}{x \cdot y \cdot z \cdot a_1 \cdot b_1 \cdot c_1}.$$

Since we want this expression to be a positive integer, by the argument that a divisor of the denominator must also divide the numerator, it follows that $a_1 \mid z^2 \cdot y \cdot c_1^2 \cdot b_1$. From the coprime conditions, we find $a_1 \mid y$. Similarly, $c_1 \mid z$ and $b_1 \mid x$ can be found. Therefore, we can set positive integers x_1, y_1, z_1 such that:

$$y = a_1 \cdot y_1, \quad z = c_1 \cdot z_1, \quad x = b_1 \cdot x_1.$$

Substituting these into the expression and performing the simplifications, we get:

$$\frac{y_1^2 \cdot x_1 \cdot a_1^3 + x_1^2 \cdot z_1 \cdot b_1^3 + z_1^2 \cdot y_1 \cdot c_1^3}{a_1 \cdot b_1 \cdot c_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1}.$$

By the same argument, we find $x_1 \mid z_1^2 \cdot y_1 \cdot c_1^3$. Since x_1 is coprime with y_1, z_1, c_1 , it follows that $x_1 = 1$. Similarly, we obtain $x_1 = y_1 = z_1 = 1$. Hence, we have:

$$a = a_1^2 \cdot b_1, \quad b = b_1^2 \cdot c_1, \quad c = c_1^2 \cdot a_1, \quad abc = (a_1 \cdot b_1 \cdot c_1)^3.$$

This completes the proof.

Now, we will move on to more challenging problems by solving IMO 2018 Problem 5. Although the standard solution involves a p -adic valuation, by applying our technique, we will solve the problem in a much shorter and simpler manner.

3.3 IMO 2018 Problem 5

Let a_1, a_2, \dots be an infinite sequence of positive integers. Suppose that there is an integer $N > 1$ such that, for each $n \geq N$, the number

$$\frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2}{a_3} + \dots + \frac{a_{n-1}}{a_n} + \frac{a_n}{a_1}$$

is an integer. Prove that there is a positive integer M such that $a_m = a_{m+1}$ for all $m \geq M$.

Solution: Let

$$S_n = \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2}{a_3} + \dots + \frac{a_{n-1}}{a_n} + \frac{a_n}{a_1}.$$

Given the conditions, each element of the sequence S_N, S_{N+1}, \dots must be a positive integer. Therefore, for every $n \geq N$, the expression

$$S_{n+1} - S_n = \frac{a_n}{a_{n+1}} + \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_1} - \frac{a_n}{a_1}$$

must also be an integer. Taking a common denominator, we obtain:

$$\frac{a_n}{a_{n+1}} + \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_1} - \frac{a_n}{a_1} = \frac{a_1 \cdot a_n + a_{n+1}^2 - a_n \cdot a_{n+1}}{a_1 \cdot a_{n+1}}.$$

Let $\gcd(a_1, a_n, a_{n+1}) = d$. Then dividing both the numerator and the denominator by d^2 , we obtain a situation where $\gcd(a_1, a_n, a_{n+1}) = 1$. Since the condition and the

statement we want to prove remain unchanged, we can assume without loss of generality that $d = 1$.

For positive integers x, y, z , using the GCD Triple Method for $d = 1$, we have:

$$\gcd(a_1, a_n) = x, \quad \gcd(a_1, a_{n+1}) = y, \quad \gcd(a_n, a_{n+1}) = z,$$

and there exist integers b_1, b_2, b_3 such that:

$$a_1 = x \cdot y \cdot b_1, \quad a_n = x \cdot z \cdot b_2, \quad a_{n+1} = z \cdot y \cdot b_3.$$

Substituting these into the original expression, we get:

$$\frac{a_1 \cdot a_n + a_{n+1}^2 - a_n \cdot a_{n+1}}{a_1 \cdot a_{n+1}} = \frac{x^2 \cdot y \cdot z \cdot b_1 \cdot b_2 + y^2 \cdot z^2 \cdot b_3^2 - z^2 \cdot x \cdot y \cdot b_2 \cdot b_3}{y^2 \cdot x \cdot z \cdot b_1 \cdot b_3}.$$

Since every number dividing the denominator must also divide the numerator, we have $x \mid y^2 \cdot z^2 \cdot b_3^2$. However, since x is coprime with y, z, b_3 , we find $x = 1$. Similarly, by the same reasoning, $y = 1$.

Substituting these values, we get

$$\frac{z \cdot b_1 \cdot b_2 + z^2 \cdot b_3^2 - z^2 \cdot b_2 \cdot b_3}{z \cdot b_1 \cdot b_3} = \frac{b_1 \cdot b_2 + z \cdot b_3^2 - z \cdot b_2 \cdot b_3}{b_1 \cdot b_3}.$$

Thus, $b_3 \mid b_1 \cdot b_2$. Since b_3 is coprime with b_1 and b_2 , we find $b_3 = 1$. Therefore, $a_n = z \cdot b_2$ and $a_{n+1} = z$, which implies $a_{n+1} \mid a_n$.

Thus, our sequence is non-increasing, and by Fermat's infinite descent method, the sequence will eventually stabilize. This completes the proof.

3.4 Taiwan Mathematical Olympiad 2024

Given that the conditions for positive integers x, y, z

- $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$
- $x \mid yz(x + y + z)$
- $y \mid xz(x + y + z)$
- $z \mid xy(x + y + z)$
- $x + y + z \mid xyz$

Prove that $xyz(x + y + z)$ is square of an integer.

Solution: Similar to previous problems, let $\gcd(x, y) = a, \gcd(y, z) = b$ and $\gcd(x, z) = c$. From the GCD Triple Method, we can express x, y and z as:

$$x = a \cdot c \cdot x_1, \quad y = a \cdot b \cdot y_1, \quad z = b \cdot c \cdot z_1$$

where x_1, y_1 and z_1 are positive integers.

Substituting into the given conditions, we find:

- $x_1|b^2(x + y + z)$,
- $y_1|c^2(x + y + z)$,
- $z_1|a^2(x + y + z)$,
- $x + y + z|a^2b^2c^2x_1y_1z_1$

Since $\gcd(x, y) = a$, we have $\gcd(x_1, b) = 1$, which means that x_1 must divide $x + y + z$. Similarly, using the same approach for y_1 and z_1 , we conclude:

$$x_1y_1z_1|x + y + z|a^2b^2c^2x_1y_1z_1$$

Given that $\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(x, y, z) = 1$ and $\gcd(y, z) = b$, we find: $\gcd(a, b \cdot c \cdot z_1) = 1$ and $\gcd(a, x + y + z) = \gcd(a, b \cdot c \cdot z_1) \leq \gcd(a, b) \cdot \gcd(a, c \cdot z_1) = 1$ Thus:

$$\gcd(a \cdot b \cdot c, x + y + z) = 1, x + y + z|x_1 \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1$$

Therefore,

$$x + y + z = x_1 \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1 \text{ and } xyz(x + y + z) = (abc \cdot x_1y_1z_1)^2$$

This confirms that $xyz(x + y + z)$ is indeed a perfect square. The proof is complete.

3.5 EMC 2024 Junior Problem 1

Show that if the equation

$$\gcd(a, b) + \gcd(a, c) + \gcd(b, c) = b + c + 2023$$

holds, then $\gcd(b, c) = 2023$

Solution:

Let $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$, $\gcd(a, b) = d \cdot x$, $\gcd(a, c) = d \cdot y$ and $\gcd(b, c) = d \cdot z$

Because $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$, we have:

$$a = d \cdot x \cdot y \cdot a_1$$

$$b = d \cdot x \cdot z \cdot b_1$$

$$c = d \cdot y \cdot z \cdot c_1$$

where a_1, b_1 and c_1 are positive integers.

Substituting these into the equation, we get:

$$d(x + y + z) = dz(y \cdot c_1 + x \cdot b_1) + 2023$$

Thus, $d|2023$, so let $2023 = d \cdot k$. Substituting this into the equation:

$$d(x + y + z) = d \cdot z \cdot (y \cdot c_1 + x \cdot b_1) + d \cdot k$$

Simplifying, we obtain:

$$x + y + z = z \cdot (y \cdot c_1 + x \cdot b_1) + k$$

From this we derive:

$$z \geq (z - 1) \cdot (x + y) + k$$

For this inequality to hold, $z = 1$ and $k = 1$. Therefore, $d \cdot k = 2023$ implies $d = 2023$. Since $z = 1$, we have $\gcd(b, c) = d \cdot z = 2023$

This completes the proof.

4. Results and Discussion

Let a, b, c be integers such that $\gcd(a, b, c) = d$, $\gcd(a, b) = d \cdot x$, $\gcd(a, c) = d \cdot z$ and $\gcd(b, c) = d \cdot y$. Then there exist positive integers a_1, b_1 and c_1 pairwise coprime, such that the following equalities hold:

- $a = d \cdot x \cdot z \cdot a_1$
- $b = d \cdot x \cdot y \cdot b_1$
- $c = d \cdot y \cdot z \cdot c_1$

It has been observed that this method is effective for solving certain problems, often yielding results more quickly and easily than the original solution. These solutions have been structured in a way that can be understood by a high school-level student. However, the method we discovered is applicable to three distinct positive integers. By further developing this method, it could be extended to n different positive integers by defining the greatest common divisor of every pair, every triple, and similarly, the greatest common divisor of any n -tuple.

4.1 Suggestions

- The method we developed applies to three distinct positive integers. However, this method can be extended to n distinct positive integers by defining the gcd (greatest common divisor) for each pair, each triple, and similarly the gcd for any set of n integers.
- In general, for n distinct positive integers, there are $\binom{n}{2}$ possible pairs of numbers. Each pair (a_i, a_j) can have a corresponding greatest common divisor $\gcd(a_i, a_j)$. When extending the GCD Triple Method to n integers, we therefore define $\binom{n}{2}$ pairwise gcd values:

$$G_{ij} = \gcd(a_i, a_j) \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq i < j \leq n.$$

For $n = 3$, this gives exactly $\binom{3}{2} = 3$ pairwise gcds, matching the classical GCD Triple structure. This combinatorial perspective shows that the general case involves $\binom{n}{2}$ gcd relations and can potentially lead to higher-order analogues, such as GCD quadruples or GCD n -tuples. This observation suggests a natural generalization of our method to any finite set of integers, by systematically defining gcds over all $\binom{n}{2}$ pairs.

- For other unresolved problems, different methods could be found by defining gcd and lcm (least common multiple) for various pairs of integers. Moreover, higher-order data (e.g., the $\binom{n}{3}$ triple gcds) may lead to refined decompositions and uniqueness statements; we leave such extensions as natural directions for future work.

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5. Appendices

5.1 LTE LEMMA

Definition Let $p \geq 2$ be a prime number and let a and b be coprime positive integers such that $p|a - b$. Then, for every positive integer n , we have

- $\nu_p(a^n - b^n) = \nu_p(n) + \nu_p(a - b)$.

In the case where $p = 2$ and x, y are odd positive integers, for an even n , this equality takes the form

- $\nu_2(x^n - y^n) = \nu_2(x - y) + \nu_2(x + y) + \nu_2(n) - 1$

(Parvardi, 2011).